

A Brief Theoretical Examination of the Developmental Process of Continuous Learning and Teaching: From Antegogy to Gerontogy

Noel Kok Hwee Chia EdD, BCET, BCSE, FCP, FCoT, FCoHP
Assistant Professor
Early Childhood & Special Needs Education
National Institute of Education
Nanyang Technological University, Singapore

ABSTRACT

There are many different theories of how people learn and how different people learn differently. Hence, literature on the various teaching methods to meet these diversified learning styles and needs is plentiful. However, very little, if none at all, has been written to show learning and teaching/training as an intertwining continuous developmental process that begins at birth through childhood and adolescence to old age for a typical learner as well as an atypical learner. This paper is an attempt to examine that often forgotten learning-teaching/learning-training process that develops and changes continuously throughout one's lifetime.

Key words: Development, Learning, Process, Teaching, Training

Introduction

Teaching and learning constitute what we call education, which in its broadest sense, is defined as the process by which society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to the next with formative impact on the mind, character and physical ability of an individual and by which the individual learns. Teaching facilitates learning and learning prepares for future employability and further development.

However, learning does not stop once an individual has found employment in the workforce. It has become a "lifelong, voluntary, and self-motivated" (Department of Education & Science, 2000) in one's pursuit of knowledge for either personal or professional reasons. Known as lifelong learning, it not only enhances social inclusion, active citizenship and personal development, but also competitiveness and employability (Rojvithee, 2005).

Learning is no longer limited to formal education in schools today. It has become a developmental process of continuous building of knowledge and skills throughout an individual's lifetime involving formal, informal and/or non-formal experiences encountered daily (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Developmental Model of Learning Process

The European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (2004) has divided learning into three different inter-related forms: formal, informal and non-formal. Each of the three forms is briefly described below:

Formal Learning: This form of intentional learning involves a structured programme in terms of learning objectives, duration and support provided by an educational institution or training centre and it leads learners to some form of certification.

Informal Learning: This form of learning may be intentional or non-intentional and involves daily life activities related to work, family or leisure. Without a structured programme, this form of learning does not result in any form of certification for the learners.

Non-formal learning: This form of intentional learning involves a structured programme or as part of an organised activity that takes place within a workplace or community. However, it does not lead to certification or qualification for the learners.

The aim of this paper is to examine the often forgotten learning-teaching/learning-training or teaching-learning/training-learning (used interchangeably) process as a continuous development that grows and changes throughout an individual's lifetime (see Figure 2): from birth to old age for a typical learner as well as to touch briefly on that of an atypical learner.

Figure 2: Developmental Process of Continuous Learning

Antegogy/Autogogy: Spontaneous Leading of Self (from birth to 6 years old)

From the first day when a child is born until it is time for him/her to attend a play-group or nursery, the child already has begun learning. From the reception of visual and auditory inputs as well as touch by the primary caregivers and other well-wishers, the child is picking up multiple sensory signals, comprehending and managing the information by integration and modulation of his/her senses in order to make meaning. The three key factors involved here are: comprehensibility, manageability and meaningfulness; they constitute what has been termed as the sense of coherence (Antonovsky, 1987). A breakdown in this sense of coherence will be disastrous to the child as in the case of those with learning disabilities (Margalit, 1998) and, in turn, will also impact on the parents, especially mothers (Al-Yagon & Cinamon, 2008).

It is during this period from birth to 6 years of age that a lot of intuitive learning is happening. For instance, mathematical knowledge initially develops qualitatively and toddlers are able to judge quantities by determining meaning only in relation to another such as two cookies are more than one. Between 1½ years old and beginning of 2 years old, young children can pick three cookies over two and so on. This intuitive ability, known as *subitizing* (Clements & Sarama, 2009) or more specifically, perceptual subitizing (Clements et al., 1999) allows these children to recognize number and change in number.

However, the *real* teaching has not begun yet. It sets as the foundation for future learning habits and resourcefulness. This is probably the developmental phase with the highest amount of informal learning as children imitate almost everything from parents, peers and their environment that affects all the other learning abilities later in life. This phase of incidental learning or teaching is what I have termed as *antegogy*, where the two Greek words *ante* means “before” and *gogy* or *gogia* means “to lead”; literally it means “before leading” or put it in another way, the before *formal* learning begins to take the lead.

Learning during this period is also spontaneous and is often described as ‘learning is caught’. Such a phenomenon has been observed to take place during the critical or sensitive period between 2 and 5 years of age (Lenneberg, 1967; Santrock, 1995). This is based on the critical period hypothesis that there is an ideal window period that young children can acquire a first language if presented with adequate stimuli (Robertson, 2002). After that period, it is believed that the pace of learning slows down and becomes a deliberate effort. This critical period hypothesis has been fiercely debated for decades and several studies have suggested that the phase should be termed as optimal period to be more accurate.

Young children are by nature instinctively inquisitive learners who can *absorb* knowledge and experience from daily contacts with their environments (e.g., through exploration and games) and the people (e.g., through conversation and play) surrounding them. They play the role of both learner and teacher as one to themselves and learning to them is unconscious and automatic. I call this form of learning *autogogy* where *auto* means “self” and the term literally means “to lead by self”. Montessori (1967) described such children as having an “absorbent mind” to learn about themselves, the people around them and their environment. However, when a child is too absorbed with himself/herself over a specific task such that he/she keeps repeating it or becomes too obsessive, autogogy works against him/her for his/her own good. Such a child loses touch with his/her environment and is often described as having autistic tendency,

Moreover, should the child be pushed or compelled to learn beyond his/her level of readiness and the limits of intrinsic motivation, he/she would soon lose interest in learning and might even become a resistant or reluctant learners.

However, parents today are sending their infants and toddlers to all kinds of headstart programmes believing that such learning (or hot-housing) will not only enrich or enhance their cognitive abilities but also expedite their cognitive development and prepare them to succeed in formal education later on. My argument against such programmes is that they are not beneficial and are too pressurizing to young learners (Gallaher & Coche, 1987); this is not exactly how a young child learns naturally.

Pedagogy: Leading the Child (from 6 to 24 years old)

Formal learning between 6 and 24 years of age primarily takes place in educational institutions, while families, religious institutions, social communities and mass media continue to provide non-formal and informal learning. Beginning with the primary education through secondary to post-secondary and/or tertiary education, the main aim of teaching and learning is to provide holistic development of learners' physical, intellectual, socio-emotional and mental capabilities. In Singapore, the schooling process attempts to draw the best out of each child, helping each to maximize his/her potential (Goh, 1979; Ho & Gopinathan, 1999).

Learning has become deliberate and is "taught" and an adult such as the child's parent or teacher comes into picture. Formal learning in school is also known as instrumental learning and term used to describe it is *pedagogy*, where *peda* or *paida* means "child"; so it literally means "to lead the child". Generally, the term refers to strategies of instruction and occasionally means the correct use of instructive strategies. Today, pedagogy is also the study of being a teacher or the process of teaching.

As instrumental learning, pedagogy "places learning at the service of government, political power and the economy" (Hinchliffe, 2001, p.31). As a result, when learning is construed as pedagogy, its results must be observable and measurable because the aim of learning is to equip learners for specified social, political and economic requirements. In Singapore, the implication is clear: "to equip the young with the skills to earn a living, to have sound moral values and, as they grow up, to become responsible adults and loyal citizens" (Ho & Gopinathan, 1999, p.100).

Andragogy: Leading the Adult (from 21 to 60 years old)

As a child matures from childhood through adolescence into adulthood, his/her self-concept moves from that of a dependent personality towards one of a self-directing human being. Learning during the working life of the 21-60 year-age group is totally different from the previous age group of full-time school-age learners. The most potent motivations of this group of adult learners are internal rather than external and these learners need to know why they need to learn something (Holton, Swanson, & Naquin, 2001; Knowles, 1984).

As an adult, learners now accumulate a growing reservoir of experience and knowledge – a rich source for learning and problem solving. They can learn informally through the use of

instructional media, mostly from their jobs, workplaces, colleagues, mass media and information technologies as well as their environment and the nature. Hence, an adult needs continuous development of intellect, capability and integrity.

The readiness of an adult to learn is closely related to the developmental tasks of his/her social role. Moreover, there is also “a change in time perspective as people mature – from future application of knowledge to immediacy of application. Thus, an adult is more problem-centered than subject-centered in learning” (Knowles, 1980, p.44-45). This form of adult learning is certainly very different from pre-adult schooling. Knowles (1968) has termed it *andragogy* (*andra* means “man/adult” and *gogy* means “to lead” in Greek), literally means “to lead the adult”.

The European concept of andragogy, meaning “the art and science of helping adults learn” (McClusky, Illeris, & Jarvis, 2007, p.84), was contrasted with pedagogy, “the art and science of helping children learn” (Knowles, 1980, p.43). Knowles (1980) has argued that pedagogy-andragogy represents a continuum ranging from teacher-directed to student-directed learning and that both approaches are appropriate with children and adults, depending on the situation.

Andragogy can be divided into the following four phases of training and learning (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Phases of Andragogy

- **Pre-vocational Training**

This refers to the pre-vocational education provided by various private and public vocational and industrial training centres. This training is mainly designed to introduce participants to the world of work and to prepare them for entry into further vocational or technical programmes. Successful completion of such programmes does not lead to a labour-market relevant vocational or technical qualification (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2002).

- **Vocational Training**

This refers to vocational education and training (also known as technical education and training) provided by vocational or technical training institutes and polytechnics that prepare trainees by developing expertise in a specific group of techniques and/or for jobs that are based on manual or practical activities. Traditionally, vocational training is considered as non-academic and is often related to a specific trade. It is classified as teaching procedural knowledge (e.g., hands-on experience and problem-based learning).

- **Professional Training**

Professional training involves development of skills and knowledge required for an individual's personal development as well as career advancement. It is often provided by polytechnics, universities and professional associations. The training covers all types of facilitated learning opportunities, ranging from university degrees to formal coursework, seminars, conferences and informal learning opportunities (Speck & Knipe, 2005).

- **Workplace Training**

Workplace training or learning provided by the employer is a subset of andragogy as well as life learning, which refers to 'the change that people undergo as a direct consequence of learning how to get along in the world' (Rothwell, 2002:8). It can take place during vocational or professional training/learning. The change that individuals undergo is to prepare themselves to perform their work, as they carry out their work, or as they reflect on their work experience. It includes "the knowledge, skills, and attitudes people need to perform their work tasks; what they must know, do, or feel to interact with others to achieve results, and what they come to learn about themselves and their own learning style and learning process" (Rothwell, 2002, p.8).

Gerontology: Leading the Old Adult (from 60 years old and above)

In a decade or two, our workforce population is greying. Statistics provided by the Singapore Manpower Ministry show that in June 2006, 52 percent of Singapore's workforce was above the age of 40 and this group will make up at least 55 percent of the workforce by 2015 (Hong, 2008). According to Hong (2008), *reverse apprentice*, whereby an older worker has a younger mentor, helps integrate the greying workforce into the ever-changing workplace. Joyce Gloria (cited in Hong, 2008), the president of The Herman Group, said that "[T]he opportunity is not only to have mentorship going from the older worker to the younger worker, but have your younger workers also help your older workers acclimate to the new technologies. We call those *reverse apprenticeships*."

Learning in old age (over 60 years old) goes beyond reverse apprenticeship. To the elderly people, including those who are still employed and those have retired from the workforce, they can continue to learn a great deal from activities appropriate to their age and needs such as, aesthetic appreciation (art and music), sports and games for the elderly and social work. They should be highly respected and valued by our society for their wealth of experience and tacit knowledge to provide intellectual support to the local communities. These elderly people can also carry out voluntary work as well as being entrusted with advisory responsibility in

community centres, clubs and associations. Such activities make their lives meaningful as well as bringing invaluable benefits to society as a whole.

I have termed this form of learning-teaching process as *gerontogogy*, where the Greek word *geronto* means “old man/adult”. Literally, gerontogogy means “to lead the old adult”.

In the Appendix, examples of some suggested activities appropriate for each of the developmental phases of learning-teaching/teaching-learning process are provided.

Psychogogy: Leading the Mind (from birth to old age)

Finally, the atypical learners are not to be forgotten. In Singapore, they may be attending mainstream or special schools. For most of them, pedagogy and andragogy are not appropriate. When we use either pedagogy or andragogy, we are teaching typical students or training typical adults in a typical learning situation. However, individuals with special needs do not benefit from these teaching/training approaches. An alternative approach – be it corrective, remedial, assistive or compensatory – is needed to help these learners with challenging issues.

Known as *psychogogy*, where the Greek word *psycho* means “mind”, the term literally means to ‘to lead the mind’. It was first coined by Maslow (1943, 1965) to address the mental health of a person by developing through a hierarchy of needs towards self-actualization. According to Chia and Ng (2011), psychogogy is an “instructive theory that includes psychological influence on a learner’s mind in terms of his/her learning and thinking abilities (cognition), feelings (affect) and will (conation) to perform or act and whose behavioural traits interlinked by various senses through different sensory processes (sensation) in order to establish his/her own perception and belief through interaction with others within a given socio-cultural context” (p.2).

Psychogogy cuts through all other form of teaching and learning approaches, beginning at birth through childhood and adolescence to adulthood at ripe old age (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Psychogogy across the Ages

In this form of teaching-learning process, the most important step to be taken in order to impart knowledge and skills to atypical learners is to know their strengths and weaknesses in terms of the following building blocks of abilities and skills (see Figure 5) that should be assessed properly by qualified professionals such as psychologists, therapists and counsellors:

Figure 5: *Developmental Blocks of Learning Skills (Chia, 2008)*

Foundation Block: Learning is built on the innate abilities which are inherited and genetically coded at birth. Although a child's upward ceiling performance is defined by innate abilities, how near the child comes to performing at those upper limits is determined by other elements such as interest and motivation necessary to learning (Franken, 2002). It is these innate abilities that the child is assessed using an IQ test to determine if he/she is highly-able, able, less-able or disabled in his/her performance as a learner.

Block II: Sensory-motor skills are developed on the foundation of the child's innate abilities. It covers sensory and motor skills which are partially determined by genetic code and partly acquired through repeated interaction with the environment (Chia, 2008). Such skills can be improved with proper practice. Sensory skills refer to those such as vision, hearing, touch, smell and taste. They are most essential for receiving information. Motor skills relate to muscles and movement, and include crawling, walking, running, handwriting and speaking. Motor skills give expression to the information our senses receive and process. If there be any deficiency in any of these skills, the psychogogic approach should include sensory integration therapy, occupational therapy and/or physical therapy (Chia, 2008).

Block III: Adaptive behavioural skills as an essential learning process refer to “the effectiveness or degree with which an individual meets the standards of personal independence and social responsibility expected of his/her age and social group” (Grossman, 1973, p.11). A wide range of skills are covered at different developmental stages. During infancy and early childhood, the adaptive behavioural process of learning covers sensory-motor skills, communication skills, self—help skills and socialisation skills. During the late childhood and early adolescence, it covers application of basic academic skills in everyday life activities, application of appropriate reasoning and judgment in mastery of the environment, and social skills. Finally, during late adolescence and adulthood, it concerns vocational and social responsibility and performance. For any child with adaptive behavioural deficits, an assessment such as the Vineland Adaptive Behaviour Scales needs to be administered. The psychogogic treatment will include “applied behaviour analysis that involves systematically arranging environmental events to produce desired changes in his/her behaviour” (Chia, 2008, p.30).

Block IV: Socio-emotional behavioural skills are concerned with good people skills. According to Kratiwohi, Bloom, and Massa (1964), the socio-emotional domain encompasses qualities that are pre-requisites for socially acceptable behaviours in children, such as desirable interests, attitudes, values, and character development. Learning in this domain is often challenging because of its subjective nature. “Unlike sensory-motor and cognitive skills that can be evaluated by written examination or practical testing, socio-emotional behavioural skills are difficult to identify, quantify, and assess” (Chia, 2008, p.30). The psychogogic approach to remedy deficits in this area of concern includes social skill training, behaviour modification, play therapy and counselling.

Block V: Cognitive skills involved in learning are essential to children processing sensory information they receive. These include their ability to analyse, evaluate, retain information, recall experiences, make comparisons and determine action (Giles, 2005). Although learning as a cognitive process has an innate component, its bulk of cognitive skills are learned or deliberately acquired. When this development fails to take place naturally, cognitive weaknesses are the result and they diminish a child’s ability to learn, and are difficult to correct without specific and suitable psychogogic intervention. Cognitive skills can be practiced and improved with the right teaching. Using the appropriate strategy, the brain of a struggling learner can actually be “rewired” and cognitive function can be restored or enhanced (Goswami, 1998). Feuerstein, Rand, and Hoffman (1979) and Feuerstein et al. (2002) have termed this ability as cognitive modifiability. While weak cognitive skills can be strengthened, normal cognitive skills can be enhanced to increase ease and performance in learning. That is why enrichment programmes such as phonics, speech and drama offered outside the regular school system still play an important role in educating the child.

All the building blocks of learning and behaviour briefly discussed above are essential to a child studying academic subjects such as Mathematics and Science in formal instruction or pedagogy. Although the knowledge base of each academic subject can be expanded, without the proper foundation of earlier learning and behavioural skills, academic progress can become a difficult and frustrating challenge, especially to the child with special needs. Hence, psychogogy, involving remedial teaching and intensive coaching, is dependent on an accurate psycho-

educational assessment of these building blocks to design an appropriate individualised education plan to help such a learner.

For example, after a battery of tests has been completed and results analysed, the learner's psycho-educational profile is established, i.e., taking his/her chronological age (CA) and mental age (MA) as benchmarks, all the other equivalent ages will be recorded and compared with these two age benchmarks. If the learner's CA is 7 years 6 months and his MA is found to be 8 years 6 months, it means the learner's intellectual capacity is one year ahead of his CA. He should be able to perform academic tasks (e.g., reading, spelling, comprehension and mathematics) at 8½ years old despite being a 7½-year-old child. However, if the learner's equivalent ages for academic tasks/skills are at his CA, it suggests that the learner's potential has not been maximised. If these equivalent academic ages are two years below MA or CA, we can say that there are some suspected learning challenges such as dyslexia and dyscalculia.

Depending on the findings of the psycho-educational evaluation and profiling, an appropriate intervention plan is needed and must be designed according to the assessment results in order to meet the learner's learning and behavioural needs. All intervention strategies and activities are carefully selected to be incorporated into the learner's individualised education plan. These chosen strategies and activities put together form the blueprint for treatment which becomes the approach to work with the learner concerned. This is psychogogy, i.e., leading the mind: for children with special needs, I term the instructional approach as *psycho-pedagogy*; and for adults and older adults with disabilities, I use the term *psycho-andragogy* and *psycho-gerogogy* respectively.

How well learners with special needs are going to perform and benefit from specialised instruction provided by special education teachers and/or allied educators who depend heavily on their own levels of consciousness in terms of cognitive, conative, affective and sensory awareness (Chia, 2011; Hawkins, 2006). Psychogogy takes into consideration the different levels of consciousness in the mind of an atypical learner in order to bring out the best in his/her behavioural development and to maximise his/her learning potential. Not only is psychogogy appropriate and beneficial to atypical learners, it will also enhance the development of typical learners and sharpen their learning mind. Psychogogy might well become the teaching-learning approach of the 21st century.

REFERENCES

- Al-Yagon, M., & Cinamon, R.G. (2008). Work-family relations among mothers of children with learning disorders. *European Journal of Special needs Education*, 23(2): 91-107.
- Antonovsky, A. (1987). *Unraveling the mystery of health: How people manage stress and stay well*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Chia, N.K.H. (2008). Educating the whole child in a child with special needs: What we know and understand and what we can do. *ASCD Review*, 14: 25-31.

- Chia, N.K.H. (2011). *Cognitive consciousness in children with mental retardation*. Retrieved February 27, 2011, from <http://www.lsesnet.com/blog/index.php?paged=2>.
- Chia, N.K.H., & Ng, A.G.T. (2011). *Psychology: Redesigning pedagogy for special and allied educators*. Retrieved March 26, 2011, from <http://www.lsesnet.com/blog/>.
- Clements, D.H., & Sarama, J. (2009). *Learning and teaching early math: The learning trajectories approach*. New York: Routledge.
- Clements, D.H., Swaminathan, S., Zeitler-Hannibal, M.A., & Sarama, J. (1999). Young children's concepts of shape. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 30(2): 192–212.
- Department of Education and Science (2000). *Learning for Life: White Paper on Adult Education*. Dublin, Republic of Ireland: Stationery Office.
- European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (2004). *Terminology of vocational training policy: A multilingual glossary for an enlarged Europe*. Retrieved March 9, 2011, from <http://www.cedefop.europa.eu/EN/about-cedefop/projects/validation-of-non-formal-and-informal-learning/european-inventory-glossary.aspx>
- Feuerstein, R., Feuerstein, R.S., Falik, L.H., & Rand, Y. (2002). *The dynamic assessment of cognitive modifiability: The learning propensity assessment device: Theory, instruments and techniques*. Jerusalem, Israel; The International Centre for the Enhancement of Learning Potential.
- Feuerstein, R., Rand, Y., & Hoffman, M.R. (1979). *The dynamic assessment of retarded performers: The learning potential assessment device, theory, instruments, and techniques*. Baltimore, MD: University Park Press.
- Franken, R.E. (2002). *Human motivation (5th Edition)*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Thomson Learning.
- Gallagher, J.M., & Coche, J. (1987). Houshousing: the clinical and educational concerns over pressuring young children. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 2(3): 203-210.
- Giles, B. (Ed.) (2005). *Thinking and knowing*. Kent, UK: Grange Books.
- Goswami, U. (1998). *Cognition in children*. London, UK: Psychology Press.
- Grossman, H.J. (Ed.) (1973). *Manual on terminology and classification in mental retardation*. Washington, DC: American Association on Mental Deficiency.
- Hawkins, D.R. (2006). *Transcending the levels of consciousness*. West Sedona, AZ Veritas Publishing.
- Hinchliffe, G. (2001). Education or pedagogy? *Journal of Philosophy of Education*, 35(1): 31-45.
- Ho, W.K., & Gopinathan, S. (1999). Recent developments in education in Singapore. *School Effectiveness and School Improvements*, 10(1): 99-117.

- Holton, E.F. III, Swanson, R.A., & Naquin, S.S. (2001). Andragogy in practice: Clarifying the andragogical model of adult learning. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 14(1): 118-143.
- Hong, L. (2008, 6 January). US experts say graying workforce adds value to manpower. Retrieved March 17, 2011, from <http://www.channelnewsasia.com/stories/singaporelocalnews/view/320998/1/.html>.
- Knowles, M.S. (1968). Andragogy, not pedagogy. *Adult Leadership*, 16(10), 350-352, 386.
- Knowles, M.S. (1980). *The modern practice of adult education: From pedagogy to andragogy* (2nd Edition). New York, NY: Cambridge Books.
- Knowles, M.S. (1984). *Andragogy in action: Applying modern principles of adult learning*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Kratliwohl, D.R., Bloom, B.S., & Masa, B.B. (1964). The need for classification of affective objectives. In B.S. Bloom (Ed.), *Taxonomy of educational objectives: Handbook II: Affective domain* (pp.15-23). New York, NY: David McKay.
- Lenneberg, E.H. (1967). *Biological Foundations of Language*. San Francisco, CA: John Wiley and Sons.
- Margalit, M. (1998). Loneliness and coherence among preschool children with learning disabilities. *Journal of learning Disabilities*, 31(2): 173-180.
- Maslow, A.H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370-396.
- Maslow, A.H. (1965). *Eupsychian management: Making good management better. A psychologist's observations about effective management practice*. Homewood, IL: Richard D. Irwin.
- McClusky, H.Y., Illeris, K., & Jarvis, P. (2007). Knowles's andragogy, and models of adult learning. In S.B. Merriam, R.S. Caffarella, & L.M. Baumgartner (Eds.), *Learning in adulthood: A comprehensive guide* (3rd Edition) (pp.83-104). San Francisco, CA: John Wiley and Sons.
- Montessori, M. (1967). *The absorbent mind*. New York, NY: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (2002). *Glossary of statistical terms*. Retrieved March 21, 2011, from <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/about.asp>.
- Robertson, P. (2002). The critical age hypothesis: A critique of research methodology. *Asian EFL Journal*. Retrieved February 28, 2011 from http://www.asian-efl-journal.com/marcharticles_pr.php
- Rojvithee, A. (2005, October 24). *Introduction to definition of lifelong learning*. Paper presented at the OECD Global Forum on Education: The Challenges for Education in a Global Economy, October 24-25, 2005, Santiago, Chile.

Rothwell, W.J. (2002). *The workplace learner: How to align training initiatives with individual learning competencies*. New York, NY: American Management Association.

Speck, M., & Knipe, C. (2005). *Why can't we get it right? Designing high-quality professional development for standards-based schools (2nd Edition)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press

Santrock, J.W. (1995). *Life-span development (5th Edition)*. Madison, WI: WCB Brown and Benchmark.

About the author

Dr Noel Kok Hwee Chia, a former Lee Kong Chian Research Fellow, is currently an assistant professor with the Early Childhood & Special Needs Education Academic Group at the National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University. He has published numerous papers in various journals here and abroad.

T&S Journal Publications

APPENDIX: Developmental Phases of Learning-Teaching/Teaching-Learning Process

Developmental Phases		Examples of Activities
Pre-Pedagogy Birth-6 years	Antegogy	Sensory stimulation, hugging, baby talk
	Autogogy	Self exploration and discovery, play
Pedagogy 6 years-24 years		Formal schooling based on the national curriculum for academic and non-academic subjects
Andragogy 21 years-60 years	Pre-Vocational training	Basic literacy and numeracy skills, computer literacy skills
	Vocational training	Specific vocational/technical skill training, practical supervision, problem-based learning, apprenticeship
	Professional training	Formal coursework, conferences, seminars
	Workplace training	Knowledge, skills and attitudes needed to perform work tasks
Gerontogogy 60 years and above		Aesthetic appreciation, sports and games, reverse apprenticeship

I do hereby solemnly declare that I/we am/are the primary author (s) of this article. This article has never been published any where else before and not being reviewed any where else at the moment. I also solemnly declare that I will take the full responsibility if there is any issue in regards to the copyright violation.